

When designing the interview questionnaire, this study considered the following items:

1. Satisfying the needs of customers: product appearance, function, physical properties, including delivery and subsequent services;
2. Compliance with laws and regulations: product material and process compliance Requirements for safety and environmental protection regulations;
3. Confirmation of research and development capabilities: The business department needs to confirm to the R&D department that the factory has the ability to meet customer needs;
4. Provide solutions: resolve issues that are not in line with expectations until the customer is satisfied.

表 3-1 Interviewee

Respondents are currently serving units	Interview object	Job title	Interview manner	time	Interview date
R&D & Development Department	Manager Lin	Manager	Face-to-face	40 min	2018.08.05
EVA Factory	Factory manager Chang	Factory	Face-to-face	50 min	2018.09.12
Rubber factory	Factory manager Chen	Factory	Face-to-face	50 min	2018.09.20
Q.C Department	Manager Luo	Manager	Face-to-face	60 min	2018.10.15
Business Department	V.P Xie	V.P manager	Face-to-face	40 min	2018.12.04

表 3-2 Interview outline

customer
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are your requirements for the appearance, function, physical properties and quality of the product? 2. How much do you know about the need for this product to comply with relevant safety and environmental regulations?
Director of R&D and production plant
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do I set the proper machine feeding temperature and time flow? 2. How do you control production quality and yield?
Raw material manufacture
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do you ensure the quality stability of EVA materials? 2. How do you make sure it's on time?

Business
Due to the company's under-utilization of orders and equipment, how do you find new sources of business?
To meet the application of the company's machinery and equipment?

**Meeting Interviews with 3 chief of Footwear Brands and manufacture manager
(average interview length 90 min)**